

COMMUNITY VIGILANTE GROUPS IN NIGERIA: A REVIEW OF ITS ACTIVITIES AND REGULATORY POLICIES

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Abstract

Vigilante groups are found in communities. Their introduction has helped filled the gaps existed in the police and other law enforcement agencies to curb crime, as they complement the efforts of security and law enforcement agencies, who have been overwhelmed by crime and criminality in most Nigeria communities. Vigilante groups came into existence in Nigeria in 1970. It was meant to combat the rising cases of criminal activities in communities. Over the years vigilante groups have become parts of the landscape of Nigeria's security agencies. The groups have also been criticized and accused of human right abuses and violation. They have been said to have engaged in extrajudicial killings and unauthorized arrest, harassment and unlawful detention of innocent citizens in their various local communities. The objectives of this study were set to find out if there are regulatory policies guiding the activities of vigilante groups; if they adhere to laid down policies establishing them; and if they have made meaningful impact on the overall security situation in the country. This study adopted quantitative and the secondary method of data generation, which is based on reported cases. The study adopted public interest theory, which is one of the key elements of regulatory theory. The study concluded that vigilante groups should be given clear responsibilities in other to collaborate meaningfully with the police and other law enforcement agencies. As it also advocated that proper training and compensation packages should be accorded to them, in line with best practices.

Key word: Vigilante groups, security agencies, regulatory policy, communities

Introduction

Adhering to strict regulatory policies geared towards the activities of vigilante groups in Nigeria would aid effectiveness, accountability, trust and efficiency in policing and managing crime and criminality in the communities and society at large. According to Oaikhena & Aligbe, (2023) quoting Frank (2009) they rightly observed that “for policies to improve regulatory compliance of the population, it must be abreast of what the target groups are yearning for or what is befitting for them to enable them leave a life of cordiality and understanding in order to key into informed regulatory design”. Insecurity is one of the problems or issues plaguing Nigeria. Most communities in Nigeria have had to deal with security challenges.

Security is a collective responsibility of all citizens. The advent of Vigilante groups in our societies today was to effectively compliment the strength and activities of the police in crime prevention and control. According to Akinlabi & IHEMEJE (2021), quoting Chuckwuma (2002), they posited that “in Africa, four typologies of vigilante have been identifies, these are i) religious vigilante; ii) ethnic vigilante; iii) state-sponsored vigilante; and iv) neighborhood or community vigilante. The police and other security law enforcement agencies has been confronted with several criminal cases emanating from communities in Nigeria. As a result, the formal introduction of vigilante groups has helped to compliment the efforts being made by security agencies in fighting crime and criminality. According to Ukanah (2011) he observed that “well-meaning Nigerians have expressed high-minded concern and outrage over killings and maiming of innocent civilians, the accompanying carnage, and the effects they have had or are capable of exerting on some aspects of our national life especially on our collective religious and political psyche, and the image of the country”.

The media is awash with reports of the uncomfortable frequency and resentment associated with crime and criminality in our communities. Akinlabi & Ihemeje (2021) while reporting on Ile Ife a community in the western part of Nigeria, said that “criminal activities seem to be more rampant in Ile-Ife due to the existence of adjacent rural areas and many roads leading to the town. They added that these has made it easier for hoodlums to invade the town from the neighborhood, and escape through the routes or ways from the metropolitan.” While Yisrael, *et al.* (2023) agreed that “in the west, the Oodua People’s Congress (OPC) has been a major vigilante group in the region”.

Vigilante groups play significant roles in ensuring that communities where they exist are crime free or reduced to the barest minimum, thereby building confidence among the people. According to Osioma (2004), he posits that “confidence is very important in all human interactions and transactions, as a socio-biological cement holding people and groups together when it exists”. Collaborative efforts with the Police and other security agencies have brought succor and reduction in crime. The need to exchange information and ideas is important to avoid rumours, misunderstanding, misconception, and misinterpretation of intentions. Most communities have had a severe carnage of crime and criminality, which had led to the destruction of properties, life and violence, this has a significant effect or impact on the development of communities and the overall wellbeing of the citizens or residence. This could be the reason why Ikelegbe (2003) observed that “the social and historical base of civil society in Africa is ignored, just as groups other than those indicated in western liberal discourse that are situated in the dynamics of Africa society and state-society relations”. As a result, social cohesion is negatively affected.

In furtherance, crime creates fear among residence, paving the way to avoid interaction and trust among individuals and even families sometimes. This invariably has led to the cycle of

economic, and security decline, as investment is jettisoned. Crime has also been linked to lose of jobs and tax issues, that could help in community development, paving the way for the introduction of vigilante groups to aid or curb the menace in the community, in order to compliment the efforts of the police. Osisioma, (2004), rightly observed that “the police is an inevitable organization in every society that desires peace, order, obedience of the laws of the land, prevention of crime, sustenance of civilized social values and standards of behaviours, including safety of lives and properties”.

The collaborative efforts between the police and vigilante groups, is to deal with few naturally inclined outlaws, violent people, and criminally inclined elements who must be kept constantly in check and forced to move along the path of law with the majority law abiding people. Those who are armed illegally to destabilize communities, whether they are part of the defence and security of the state or not, become serious threats to life and property, as the arms and ammunition they bear, becomes a source of power to do unusual and illegal things such as extortion, commandeering people’s property, rape, intimidation, humiliation, and settling old scores. Traditional approach to crime control is through deterrence, with an emphasis on detection, punishment and efforts to reform convicted criminals (Akinlabi & IHEMEJE, 2021). It was in line with these that this study sought to review the activities of vigilante groups with regards to regulatory policies and advocate for proper adherence to strict regulatory policies for the sake of effectiveness, and political stability.

Significance of vigilante groups in Nigeria communities

In a recent survey by Nextier (2024), reported by Channels Television, it indicated that between 2011 – 2020, about \$18.34 million (over 24 billion naira) has been paid to kidnappers in Nigeria. The establishment of Vigilante groups in our

communities became necessary due to the rising cases of crime, disturbances, conflict and the inadequate number of police personnel in the country to deal effectively with these criminal cases. It was also reported that, the number of police men in the country is put at 371,800 (three hundred and seventy-one thousand eight hundred) (wikipedia.org.). These could be reason why Akinlabi and IHEMEJE (2024) observed that, “the public dissatisfaction with the response of government agencies in dealing with the increasing wave of crime and disorder has induced many communities to deeply rely on self-help measures or support strategies for the protection of life and security of properties within respective neighbourhoods.

Meanwhile the United Nations standard for the police to a citizen is one (1) police officer to one hundred and fifty (150) people. The population of Nigerians is over two hundred (200) million, this invariably means that the number of police officers to a citizen is grossly inadequate, part of which vigilante groups were introduced to compliment, the efforts of the police in crime fighting and prevention, especially in the various communities. The existence of criminal gangs and hoodlums in most communities has overwhelmed the police. This could be the reason why YISRAEL, *et. al.* (2023), also observed that “...security challenges in economic and industrial cities like Onitsha, Aba and Nnewi (easter part of Nigeria) among others became worrisome as armed robbery endangered the personal safety and livelihood of market traders, manufacturers and industrialist”.

There are some tasks and roles that vigilante groups cannot perform, such tasks and roles are better performed by the police, because they are closer to civilians from their training, culture, and psychological orientation. The average policeman for example, has a higher level of tolerance than the vigilante member who could be crude in their approach, as they have not received proper training in handling civilians. This lack of training has led to illegitimacy in weapon application, as cases of

mishandling and accidental discharges have been reported by citizens in most communities against vigilante groups. Training becomes a necessity in crime prevention and weapon handling, including strategies for dispute resolution.

The prevention and respect for law and order in the society enable communities where vigilante groups exist to live their lives and pursue their daily bread in a peaceful, and orderly fashion, as the environment is secured. Thus, in the performance of their duties, vigilante groups are drawn from different families in the communities, cultural background and climes. These classes of people selected and recruited into the groups are expected to work closely with the elders in the community, resulting in mutual love, confidence, cooperation and respect. According to Yisrael *et. al.*, “participation gives way for individuals of a community to control their environment and set priorities as they integrate local knowledge, values and attitudes”.

Member of the vigilante groups are usually volunteers from the communities. They are friends, family members and neighbours from the communities. Keeping these in view, Vigilante groups are therefore aimed at doing three things. Firstly, ensuring that they do not commit acts boarding on crimes against humanity; secondly, knowing where someone else is trying to commit such crime in the community and either preventing it or apprehending the person(s); and thirdly, avoid being accused of complicity in such criminal acts. These views paved way for purpose driven social justice and also create an atmosphere for policies to regulate the activities of vigilante groups in the society, considering the fact that Nigeria has a total of 774 local government areas with several communities that are in dire need of security.

Social injustice driving insecurity

In a country where trust issues affect the psychology of the people, social injustice contributes significantly to systemic

breakdown of security. Thus, leading to inequalities, unrest, crime, psychological distress, and limited access to social amenities. Individuals who are marginalized often tend to face discrimination, and employment issues, which brings about frustration, poverty, violence and crimes, which unfortunately starts from the communities before spreading to other areas, further exacerbate insecurity. According to Oluwale, (2020), he argued that “the inability of nearly half of the entire population of the country to have their economic needs met as evidenced by the poverty line coupled with the rising frustration of the people, specifically, the youths to be free from fear and wants has further exacerbated”.

Social injustice prevents transformation and economic development. Youths in the communities are mostly affected as they become restive. In order to prevent the challenge of youth restiveness, some of the youths become engaged in the protection of security of lives and properties in the community, thus some of them forming vigilante groups. Akinlabi & Ihemeje (2021) observed that, “community vigilante groups are considered as the first concept, referring to different groups of people who take up arms to protect themselves, families and their communities when they feel the absence of the security presence of the government”. When individuals are marginalized, powerlessness, helplessness and frustrated, it creates lack of control, chronic stress and diminished sense of belonging. Diminished sense of belonging from social injustice can also undermine the capacity of a person, inability of social-knowledge, and experience. The understanding of social justice reinforces the feeling of social injustice and social cohesion, as it creates room for division and tension. As a result in communities, social injustice hinders progress and inequality fostering a circle of distress and instability, which can escalate into unrest and violence, that impact negatively on community development. In these regard vigilante groups are depended upon to rise to the occasion as state authorities failed to

make provisions for adequate security. Communities form their groups for self-defense and also to address perceived deprivation and injustice.

The feeling of injustice and insecurity could lead citizens to take justice into their own hands. This is easily attributable to lack of trust in law enforcement agencies and the desire for immediate retribution against offenders. According to Yisrael, *et. al* “It is clear that the government cannot singlehandedly manage the numerous problems confronting the people in the case of security, they therefore integrate locals as stakeholders in their communities to enhance security as they understand their neighbourhoods better and share the mutual objectives of promoting it” (2023). These bring about policies that are regulatory which are closely related to social justice, that deals with legitimacy and environmental hazards, affecting marginalization in communities. According to Sardaryan (2021) he observed that “inefficient regulation can, on the contrary, slow down business development, divert resources away from investments, hamper entry into international markets, reduce jobs and so on”. The creation of enabling environment and promotion of vulnerable population in the communities indicates that regulatory policies play significant roles in easing tensions associated with insecurity. Such tensions exploit and pollute low-income areas, as weakness is prevalent in such communities, and limiting economic opportunities. The effect of social injustice affects the working conditions that allows communities to be exploited if regulations towards the effectiveness of vigilante groups are compromised. When regulations are compromised, it would lead to special interest which is likely to undermine social justice goals. However, effective regulations require independence, accountability, transparency and meaningful public participation to serve the good of the people.

Adhering to strategic policies to regulate the activities of vigilante groups

Policies are statements that controls the activities or workings of society, they are made to regulate activities. They are targeted to addressing specific problems in the society as they are also set of actions to solves problems. According to Oaikhena (2023), “policies that are strategic are policies that are targeted towards addressing a particular problem that have been identified in a society”. The prevalence of crime and criminality in communities had led to the emergence of Vigilant groups. The fact that this groups plays significant role in the communities, does not automatically bring crime to an end. They only provide conducive climate, opportunities, goodwill, and time for negotiations to take place and remove the root causes of crime as they work in synergy with the police.

Hence, policies that are strategic in nature need to be put in place and implemented to properly regulate and guide their activities. When a group activity is regulated by policies such group is expected to play by the rules of engagement. Thus, respecting the sanctity of the community and people. This essential step brings criminals and trouble makers to book through extant laws and by-laws as provided by the constitution of Nigeria. The Nigerian constitution specifically constrains the creation of state police as being agitated for, currently by some state actors. According to critics they observed that if state police is allowed to come into fruition in Nigeria, it might bring about jurisdictional disputes between the federal government and state government, over recognition and regulations of vigilante groups where they exist. Nonetheless the study advocates that, vigilante groups should continue to perform their roles in the various communities, while channelling their activities towards the ways and means that promotes safety and respect to rules and regulation in the society.

Societies needs regulations that promotes the activities of the vigilante groups towards crime fighting, as crime and criminality stirs up in most Nigeria communities. Those who are armed, whether they are part of the defence and security apparatus of the state or community or not, become serious threat to lies and acquisition of properties, to do unusual and illegal things such as extortion, commandeering people's property, rape, intimidation, humiliation, abduction, kidnapping and settling old scores. "In the contemporary mass society, in some country, due to a combination of factors, are able to fight crime effectively only through public policing without the support of sub-state actors (Adeniyi & Olusesan, 2019)". Regulations that control the activities of vigilante groups usually deals with problems of low morale, which results from poor administration and lack of public cooperation.

Given the concept with which this study is set out to achieve, the process of reviewing regulatory policy is quite challenging to execute and adhere to successfully, as vigilante groups have not received proper training techniques and strategy to deal effectively with criminals in the community and society at large. The cruelty meted out to suspects without proper trials is often times barbaric and dehumanizing. This could be the reason why Amnesty International (2002), reported that "armed vigilante groups in Nigeria are reported to carry out extrajudicial executions and killing of suspected criminals and perpetrate acts of torture, cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment, unlawful detentions and disappearances".

Policies that are regulatory in nature takes a variety of different forms. These forms shows that numerous issues can be addressed to create a new agenda-setting to be put in place, depending on the situation. On the other hand, regulatory policy that tend to be strategic believes that policy expresses and consolidate the goals that will serve public interest as justified by the government, towards the support of the existence of vigilante

groups. This policy has paved way for understanding and interactions with community leaders, which aid proper implementation of the regulatory policies that are strategic.

In this case interactions with broad spectrum of critical mass of external interest on the activities of the vigilante groups, provides a deliberate adoption of actions that are practical for the achievement of targeted interest and the fulfilment of needs. Since public policy comprised of the objectives and presumptions that guides, the actions of government and its agencies, it then follows an attempt by the government to act in considerable manner towards the implementation of regulatory policies, with the intention of addressing specific problems to fulfil particular aims. It is the desire of the study to correspond to the consequence that were intended, as determined by the establishment of vigilante group in the community.

A significant number of changes, can be achieved and utilized to improve efficiency, effectiveness and value to build cordial relationship between vigilante groups, government, security agencies and the community. Therefore, putting purpose and practice to achieve future plans is a key component to improve the welfare and well-being of citizens. Humans are divers and continue to expand overtime, it is the responsibility of government to provide adequate security for the citizens. The proper implementation of policies serves as a basic process that the government put in place to resolving some issues, the nature of which include insecurity. According to Ossisioma (2004) “war theatres are like jungle were the survival of the fittest is the rule”. Insecurity has led to the proliferation of small arms flow around easily, and people in communities who are armed oppress those who are not armed. The presence of vigilante groups reassured the people in the communities as they are watched over, as food, water, clothing etc., and their lives are safe along with the little property they may possesses in the community.

In such situation, fostering policies to check mate and request their advice, becomes sacrosanct and very essential. Such policies should be regulatory and strategic in nature to curb their activities and proliferation. This could be the reason why Okota (2024), writing for the Vanguard Newspaper said that “in the face of escalating insecurity plaguing Nigeria, a desperate populace has found itself at a crossroads, grappling with the failure of traditional security apparatus to safeguard lives and property”. The provision of legal framework that clearly defines the roles of vigilante groups, mode of operation and scope are a necessity. Thus, putting in place regulatory policies which aides’ compliance within rules and regulation, addresses misconduct among the groups. Sardaryan (2021) observed that “in most countries, Public Government (PG) has a multi-level structure and is characterized by both the distribution of functions among departments at the national level and the allocation of regional authorities, as well as municipal authorities, the latter not being part of government but significantly influences the regulation of public relationship”. This promotes national best practices and reduce the number of criminal cases in our communities and environment for the socio-economic, and political development of our communities and the well-being of the people. From these conceptions, the study proposed some policies that are strategic in nature, to be fully implemented for the success of the activities or workings of the vigilante groups in our communities, these includes:

- ***Strategic expansion policy:*** this policy guides the government in decision making aimed at expanding the activities and role of jurisdiction of the groups in order to compliment the enforcement of laws, while making sure there are proper oversight and accountability.
- ***Vigilante group integration policy:*** this is another policy pathway for integration and transition to formal security structures, such as community policies and professionalism.

- ***Vigilante group exit strategy policy***: this policy provides opportunities for income generation and security guarantees to mitigate the risk of becoming a menace and future sources of insecurity.
- ***Oversight and accountability of vigilante groups policy***: this is another strategic policy that mandates and regulate performance reporting, community engagement and disciplinary mechanism. This is to ensure that vigilante groups are accountable to the communities they serve through extension of government.
- ***Capacity building policy for vigilante***: this policy was expected to outline programmes and training skills, for group members to ensure effectiveness and adherence to human rights standards.

These few strategic policies amongst others were expected to guide and promote the activities of the vigilante groups. Nigeria has adequate resources to contribute in the maintenance of peace and security in the communities. The advocacy for a number of bodies or non-governmental association that could aid the training or assist vigilante groups in discharging their duties is necessary, especially as members are often drawn from the communities around.

Public perception of vigilante groups

The perception of vigilante groups in Nigeria, in some communities has not been very cordial, because of the activities of some members of the group. Amnesty international (2002) reported that “allegations of extortion, harassment, arson, destruction of public properties, and armed robbery are often made against members of the group”. These attitude of members of the vigilante groups negate the very essence of its establishment. The non-cordiality of some of the members had been ascribed to lack of proper training, indiscipline and coordination. Citizens and state officials were also of the views

that they lack common training mechanism to discharge their duties, as their activities are not uniform across the communities in Nigeria, generating concerns on their effectiveness and ability to effectively control crime and criminality. Criminality though a negative phenomenon is a necessary part of every society (Onwugbushi, 2017).

In any political system like Nigeria, crime and criminality cannot be ruled out, hence the presence of Vigilante groups. In a recent data survey by Nestier (2024), anchored on Channels Television, it was revealed that 2,691 persons were reportedly kidnapped within one year of President Ahmed Bola Tinubu's administration in office (May 29th, 2023 – May 29th, 2024), out of which 1,095 had incidents while 3,959 were casualties. The most important political orientation to curb crime and criminality in communities would have been related to the use of power and authority, its acquisition and deployment towards protecting the citizens. Moreso, reports are awash on social media and print medias, that harassment, intimidation, accidental discharges and manhandling of innocent persons have characterized the activities of vigilante groups, in some communities. These reports have negatively affected and question the existence of the vigilante groups in the communities. Relating to realities on ground, the group have been said to have for instance been involved in criminal activities as well. Amarachi (2024), reported that "vigilante members of Anioma Security Watch Network in Agbor, Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria, was accused of beating a 29-year-old man, identified as Joe Philip *a.k.a* Aboy, to death, over a missing Nokia torchlight phone. The incident was said to have happened on June, 16th, 2024. Basiru, *et. al.* (2019), also observed that, "...there have been increasing concerns in policy and academic circle if vigilante groups are not themselves threat to the security not only of the communities where they operate but the country as a whole".

Thus, the impetus of some of these horizontal information stems from the desire to maintain unity of all those who have descended from a common ancestor, coupled with a desire for later defence against political intruders. To maintain internal unity in the fight against crime by vigilante groups a myth of origin should be developed, a form of guardianship instituted to become an embodiment and social connection of the people. Thereby becoming the representative of the people, repositories of ritual process as well as ritual authority that hold the communities together. This was to sustain a system whereby the vigilante groups would find the ritual authority to police the community effectively, and avoid any form of conflict with people in the community and abuse of procedures, especially as it relates to suspects.

However, these perception of vigilante groups by the public is a somewhat mixed felling. Some perceive them as necessary and active while others believe that they constitute nuisance in the communities. The most important political objects are the distribution of power and authority within a state. A process of horizontal incorporation of different villages and communities which had necessitated further social collaborations to maintain the unity of the people. It was in line with this that Kheehen (2013) wrote about the social justice principles, as he observed that “social justice is a normative concept centered on the notion of fairness and the principles of equality, equity, rights and perception”. Thus alluding to social policy, he observed that “...social policy is the most powerful tool to diffuse the values and attributes of social justice and in other to ensure equity in the distribution of material and non-material goods in society”.

Theoretical framework used for analysis

The study adopted the regulatory policy as it’s framework for analysis. This policy explored the reasons why regulations emerge in societies and the reasons for its’ influence as it also

deals with public interest theory, centered on public opinion. According to Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), it observed that “regulatory policy agenda has been forged for almost 25 years, which aimed at improving understanding of the nature of regulations as a tool of government and increasing the effectiveness of that tool”. Evie & Nowaczyk (2023) also posit that “regulatory policy gives agencies the rulemaking procedures, as they are set to achieve government objectives, in line with government policies towards the economy, as well as the sustainability of the environment”.

The activities or emergence of the vigilante groups in communities was based on public interest. Public interest leads to public opinion, which is how a comprehensive theory should be and what its function and place should be in research as they influence each other significantly. Collective views and beliefs of community reflects public opinion while the welfare and well-being of the general public reflects public interest. “Whether social provisioning programme are “universal” or “targeted” is a policy choice that depends on government resources” (Kheehen, 2013).

The protection of life and properties in the communities are the responsibility of the police but complimented by the vigilante groups. Economic and social objectives are associated with regulatory policies for the interest of the people, in the community. The relationship shared with the community in this regard is important, as social interactions and emotional well-being is maintained. Oluwale, (2020) observed that “...while across known histories of societies the human societies had always developed within the confines of the limits of social justice, the security or otherwise of societies had always been directly proportional to their level of social justice”.

Regulatory theory builds social cohesion and tolerance as community dynamics is further influenced through regulatory practices and individual outcomes. Regulatory policies reflect the

community's values and norms, that governs social interactions, shaping value and encouraging a sense of belonging, through social interaction within the community. This type of regulations support emotions and contribute significantly to healthy outcomes. Crime control can be handled effectively by the vigilante groups due to regulatory framework. According to Kheehen (2013), "the failure of social policies to achieve social justice goals in many countries is often attributed to a number of interlinked concerns, namely, the successive liberalization of services in the aftermath of the neoliberal turn and the subsequent "projectizing" approach to social protection". As a result, regulatory theory can be legitimate and play societal roles with cordial interactions between the community and the vigilante groups. It helps to restore perceived inadequacies in a formal regulatory system. Due to this fact, the vigilante groups respond to perceived inadequacies in formal regulation, reflecting a community's need for security and order. This underscores their importance in community policing as illustrated in fig 1 below:

Source: Authors diagram 2024

Fig. 1 above depicts that vigilante groups are at the apex, in the diagram, and they must be guided by policies to sustain them in the fight against crime and criminality in communities, by corroborating with police and other security agencies. This collaboration can sustain the fight against crime and criminality in the communities, and can only be achieved through strategic regulatory policies, influenced by public interest and opinion. Against this backdrop, the actions of vigilante groups must be in conformity with laid down rules and regulations of the constitution establishing them. In view of this, it is imperative to state that social policies must be in place to promote effective social justice. Thus, social justice and public interest promotes safety, accountability and transparency. According to Menshikowa, *et. al.* (2020) they argued that “at the beginning of the 21st century the term ‘transparency’ was included into the list of good governance and became one in ten most used in the media”.

Summary and Conclusion

The study has so far revealed that the vigilante groups in Nigeria need to be supported and encouraged. Their social existence was brought about by necessity to aid prevent and control crime and criminality in communities. Although there have been reported cases of excessiveness, as observed by the study, these cases however, does not underscore their relevance in the provision of adequate security in the community, as they complement the Nigeria Police and other security agencies.

The composition of the group which is made-up of voluntary individuals from the communities have been able to organize patrol, respond to security threats and curb the menace of other criminal acts in the community. Their collaboration with police had provided some form of temporary deterrence against crime, through internal mechanism. They have also been supported by elders and leaders of the various community over

time, because of their active participation in crime prevention and control. In most areas where the police lack the capacity to act, the vigilante groups have provided the needed support. The study further revealed that the vigilante groups serve as bridge between the community and law enforcement agencies, as they sometimes participate in joint patrol with the police, ensuring that their actions align with strict policy regulations. Regulations is the consequence of gregariousness because man cannot live without rules.

Recommendations

- i. Vigilante groups should be encouraged and supported by relevant governmental agencies;
- ii. Proper and adequate training should be given to vigilante groups in weapons handling and administrative capabilities;
- iii. They should be remunerated accordingly, in accordance with civil service commission rules;
- iv. Vigilante groups should avoid taking laws into their hands. Criminals caught should handed over to the police authorities for proper prosecution;
- v. The collaboration between the vigilante groups should continue, as regulatory policies should also be adhered to strictly.

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